

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

TIBBIYOT OLIYGOHLARIDA LOTIN TILI O‘QITISHNING HOZIRGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI

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Kalit so‘zlar:

Innovatsion texnologiyalar, o‘qitish usullari, og‘zaki nutq, loyiha asosidagi dars, mobil o‘qitish.

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqola o‘zbek darslarida, ayniqsa, EFL uchun nutqni o‘rgatishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo‘llash usuli sifatida “Mobil ta’lim va loyihaga asoslangan ta’lim” (PBL) qo‘llanilishini tavsiflashga bag‘ishlangan edi. Nutq og‘zaki rejimda samarali mahoratdir. Bundan tashqari, nutqni o‘rganish o‘zbek talabalari uchun foydali bo‘ladi, chunki og‘zaki muloqot sifatida gapirish boshqalar bilan muloqot qilishning keng tarqalgan usuli va nutq ko‘nikmalarini egallash chet tilini o‘rganishning eng muhim jihati hisoblanadi.

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

Key words:

Innovative technologies, teaching methods, oral speech, project-based lesson, mobile learning.

Abstract:

This article was devoted to describing the application of the Mobile Learning and Project-Based Learning (PBL) as a technique of using innovative technologies through group work in teaching speaking especially for EFL in Uzbek classes. Speaking is a productive skill in the oral mode. Besides, learning to speak will be useful for Uzbek students because speaking as verbal communication is a common way to communicate with others and mastering speaking skills is the most important aspect of learning foreign language.

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЛАТИНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ВУЗАХ

Ключевые слова:

Инновационные технологии, методы обучения, устная речь, проектный урок,

Аннотация:

Эта статья была посвящена описанию применения мобильного обучения и проектного обучения (PBL) как метода использования инновационных технологий посредством групповой работы в обучении устной речи, особенно для EFL в

In modern life, any sphere demand people to be perfect in varieties of languages that especially in education system pay great attention to teach learners to speak in foreign languages fluently. In order to expand foreign language sphere the government of Uzbekistan proclaimed several laws and orders such us: On May 6, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. It's time to create a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will become a solid foundation for the future. One of the main tasks of the structure will be the creation of methods for professional translation from the state language into foreign and from foreign languages into the state. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each educational institution, said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Based on observations which taken an account while research and teaching experiences, there are some problems that can affect the EFL in Uzbek classes students' failure in speaking English. Firstly, students do not have enough time to practice speaking a lot because the instructor spends more time teaching the structure of writing their opinion. Second, more students' lack of vocabulary range is also a big factor affecting their failure in speaking English. Students need to have a fairly large useful vocabulary since this language aspect is very important in practicing speaking in English language.

The causes of this problem were not fully identified until recently and to overcome the problems stated above, many types of strategies, methods and approaches could be applied in teaching speaking. For these reasons, we decided to try the Project Based Learning technique as an alternative for teaching speaking because many research findings say that this technique is effective for teaching speaking.

The TBL technique refers to a method allowing to do the designing, planning and carrying out tasks in order to produce, publish and present a product. Through the TBL technique, learners are engaged in purposeful communication to complete authentic activities, so that they have the opportunity to use the language in a relatively natural context and participate in meaningful activities which require authentic use of language skills.

Based on the background above, the problems of this study can be formulated as follows:

Can the speaking skills of the pupils of Uzbek classes be improved through the implementation of Modern Technology-based learning?

How affect TBL to Uzbek pupils' speech and which approaches can improve with the help of TBL in Uzbek classroom?

Whether TBL and traditional project-based learning will be helpful for the teachers to teach speaking effectively?

Teaching foreign languages demand pedagogies to be more alert and creative that's why while teaching EFL speaking and using vocabulary simultaneously. Why modern pedagogical technologies more important to teach oral speech at the EFL Uzbek classes? The process of this literature review I will give specific data about the topic.

First of all, what is the modern pedagogical innovative technology itself? Pedagogical technology is the product of the development of modern didactics and pedagogy. It is considered as a new step towards a higher level of accomplishment of tasks in all existing and improving main directions of pedagogy. Pedagogical

innovation is understood as any new teaching practice that differs from the traditional lecture with the purpose of improving learning foreign language in traditional classes.

Modern pedagogy makes space for personalized learning. It employs every pedagogical process of the modern era through their efficient teachers and able management. Their improvisation of stem education to stream is one example and proof that pupils receive nothing but the best in schools.

Modern educational technology theory is a broad and specific concept. It refers to the theory and practice of optimizing teaching with modern educational theory and information technology. Modern educational technology theory is closely not only related to university quality education but also it refers any system of education such as school and higher schools as well.

Moreover, it is obvious that, so as to organize successful lesson in English language especially in Uzbek classes to improve learners speaking the conductor need to be more ideal who should involve all the audience both passive and active pupils besides, teacher manage to grab learners' attention easily using own pedagogical skills. So, pedagogy is at the heart of teaching and learning. Focusing on pedagogies shifts the perception of teachers from technicians who strive to attain the education goals set by the curriculum to experts in the art and science of teaching.

Why is pedagogy important? Having a well-thought-out and confident pedagogy can increase the quality of teaching and the way pupils learn, helping them achieve a deeper grasp with the help of fundamental material. Students can enrich their preferred learning styles while a teaching process that supports them, and the method they would like to learn.

Effective pedagogies consists of a range of techniques, involves whole-class and structured group work, leaded to learning and individual activity. Effective pedagogies target to developing higher order thinking and meta-cognition, and make good dialogue and questioning in order to do them obviously.

Teaching oral speech is the basic target aim of every FL teachers because making a conversation in English with following all grammar rules appropriately and conveying their own opinions about any topic is shows pedagogical abilities of teachers.

Why modern technologies(multimedia, mobile phones, monitor, computer, speakers and so on) so important to boost learners' speaking? First of all, modernization life is the cause of utilizing technical tools more in any sphere which most people are addicted to use them willingly, especially, young generations. Although, there exist negative sides to the human health, they cannot ignore ICT while working or learning. That can be the effective way organizing the FLC (Foreign language classes) with the help of innovative technologies. For instance, using microphone can urge the children to speak. Watching videos and listening audio materials may enhance learners'

In addition to this, every pedagogies need to distinguish these kind of methods according to pupils level and class and while evaluating their levels can be more important. The information about teaching in Uzbek classroom and system are given briefly below:

As for the school education is provided in several types of basic education schools which offer partial and complete secondary education, adult education centers, and specialized schools and boarding schools for pupils with disabilities. General education is also available in new types of institutions for example gymnasia and lyceums, some of them attached to higher education. Literacy is practically universal for both men and women (99%). However, considering that the government is implementing a long-term program of transition, in the short-term there could be some changes in the literacy rate. Moreover, school system can create fundamental base to continue the higher level education. Nowadays, most of schools are getting decorated with modern technological tools that brings to learn the foreign language without any obstacles in Uzbek classes.

Modern technologies such as Digital tools, mobile phones, computers and tablets, can be used both for fun and for study activities. As a future teacher, we need to help children understand how to save a good balance, and to develop their study skills as they become more independent. It can be a good idea to set time limits for some of the less educational digital activities. You may want to involve your children in making the rules about how and when to use technology for different purposes.

As young learners can express their emotions, communicate with each other and react, learn the language and share their humor in their own language just as they expect them to be able to do the same in the target language. To communicate in the target language, it was observed that when they cannot find the right word, they use their native language. Therefore, it is important for teachers to set a balance with the newcomers through controlled and managed classes and at the same time allow them to enjoy natural conversations, since most of our students have little opportunity to practice conversational English outside the classroom. At the initial stage, the activity will be under the supervision of the teacher. There are several ways to represent the language “orally training and teaching have changed. Everything have been changing around, and accordingly, the attitude towards learning must change. The content of education in a modern comprehensive school remains unilateral; state standards based on an objective approach are morally outdated. Many modern teachers point to the lack of a competent approach, focused on the individuality of the pupils. Today, knowledge of English language opens a window into a large global world with its colossal flow of information and innovations. At the present stage of the development of the society, the modernization of the content of education in Uzbekistan is not least connected with the innovation processes in the organization of teaching foreign languages.

To rise to the challenge of today’s university, professors make use of many types of pedagogical innovation.

For instance professor G. V. Romanova offers various ways to use multimedia tools in the educational process, including the use of electronic lecturers, simulators, language textbooks, encyclopedias, development of situational role-playing and intellectual games using artificial intelligence, modeling processes and phenomena, providing distance learning, building control systems and testing of knowledge and skills of pupils and pupils (use of controlling programmers), creation and support of sites of educational institutions, creation of presentations of educational material, the realization of projective and research activity of pupils, etc. Also, multimedia technologies allow you to develop brighter and more interesting speaking exercises. For pupils, learning a foreign language using multimedia technology also has certain advantages. Since these technologies are new, it is interesting for pupils to deal with sources of new types of information.

And in my point of view it is also important that the assimilation of new information using multimedia technologies takes place in the form of games. The use of multimedia technologies allows pupils to independently prepare mini-activities on the subject of communication and present them. When mastering a foreign, pupils have several problems, one of which is low motivation to learn the language. In such cases, it is interactive technologies that are valuable for application, because they create such conditions when the pupils feels his success and intellectual ability. Effective collaboration and communication are basic components of such training, which aims to solve problems together, acquire monologue skills, responsibility, critical thinking, and achieve meaningful results. At the present stage in our country, the use of automated training courses for learning foreign languages is spreading. But they should be used only as an aid in teaching a foreign language. It is especially useful to use them at the stage of acquainting pupils and pupils with new language material, new samples, as well as at the stage of training. pupils have the opportunity to train to spell, study lexical material, improve understanding of the audio text, develop techniques, learn

grammar, train pronunciation. Thus, at the present stage of development of science we can say for sure that the times when sufficient proof of language acquisition was the ability to translate from a foreign language and, conversely, adapted, non-authentic texts are over. In the context of high school reform, educational technologies for teaching foreign languages must also change. Involvement of modern technologies in the process of learning a foreign language significantly expands and diversifies the program, provides access to a variety of materials, expands pupils' motivation to learn, allowing them to work on the language at a pace convenient for them, thus individualizing learning and mastering a foreign language. The level of a foreign language has become an important measurement to judge a modern person. It is important to improve one's comprehensive qualities and abilities for individuals. Network education provides a completely new way of learning for people. English teaching under web-based environment is a kind of educational mode integrating computer technology, multimedia technology, network technology and modern educational method, through the multimedia teaching information collection, transmission, processing and sharing to realize the task of English teaching. Compared with the traditional English teaching mode, network English teaching has incomparable superiority. This paper based on the advantages of network platform, according to the characteristics of higher school, referenced the college English teaching reform, proposed a set of explorations for English teaching mode, achieved satisfactory result.

Therefore, the main goal of the modern teacher is to select methods and forms of the organization of learning activities of learners who optimally meet the goal. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in education has been increasingly raised. Since the main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of a communicative culture of learners, the training of practical acquisition of foreign language, then the use of computer technology, Internet resources is the best approach in teaching. It has been quite a few years since a computer entered our life, and we no longer

imagine a modern lesson without the use of information technology. Technology becomes an integral tool in increasing learners' interest for their studying issues and developing visual-figurative thinking. It is already known, that the use of Technology in the learning process has the potential to activate cognitive, intellectual and independent activities of learners. Information technology makes it possible to significantly change the forms and methods of academic work. new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional teaching of foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real life situations that will stimulate the study of the material and develop adequate behavior. Now everyone understands that the Internet has tremendous information capabilities and no less impressive services. Whichever way we relate to the Internet, we have to recognize the fact that the worldwide network has become an integral part of modern reality. Many learners have long appreciated all the advantages of the Internet and actively use its services in their educational activities in Uzbek classes, while for teachers the space of this world web remains mostly unknown, unfamiliar and to some extent frightening. What kind of help the Internet can provide depends on how we use it for solving some didactic tasks. English teachers can use widely the resources of the global Internet. Preparing messages, learners filter a lot of information, if you need to listen to music, and most often watch photos. Such tasks for learners can be used in the preparatory stage of the lesson, for example, in combination with the method, allows learners to practically apply their knowledge, skills and abilities. This is one of the forms of organization of research and cognitive activity, in which group activity is successfully realized that allows increasing the motivation for learning a foreign language. The point of such a work process is the learners himself with the opportunity to freely express his opinion and practical use of knowledge in a foreign speech. In my lessons I use the following educational Internet resources: Fairy tales, stories, letters», and the DLR (Digital Learning Resources) used in pedagogical work enables the teacher:

- to present the material more understandable,
- in less time, with greater understanding on the part of the pupils;
- to find basic and additional materials for lessons and lectures;
- to save time for oral practice;
- to organize individual, pair and group work with class,
- simplify the control of learners learning activities;
- to increase the interest of learners, their motivation, engage in the creative process.

Thus, without the usage of Technology in the teaching process, it is difficult to imagine modern English lessons. Their usage expands the scope of the educational process, increases its practical area. The use of Technology and Internet resources in English lesson allows us to fully implement a whole range of methodological, pedagogical and psychological principles. The use of computer educational programs in English classes increases the effectiveness of solving communicative problems, develops different types of speech activity of learners, and forms a stable motivation for learners to learn foreign language activities in class. In the 21st century, the society makes ever higher demands on the practical knowledge of English in everyday communication and in the professional sphere. The volumes of information are growing, and often routine ways of its transfer, storage and processing are ineffective. The use of information technology reveals the enormous capabilities of the computer as a means of learning EFL. But we must not forget that the use of multimedia technologies can not provide a significant pedagogical effect without a teacher, since these technologies are only ways of teaching. The computer in the educational process is not a mechanical teacher, a tool that enhances and expands the possibilities of its teaching activity. And also the use of Technology and Internet resources in English lesson is important today, because the teacher should be interesting for his pupils, by keeping up to date, improving their pedagogical skills and level of intelligence. The methodological advantages of teaching a foreign language with the help of

multimedia tools show that this method has a greater degree of interactive learning, allows you to choose the pace and level of tasks, improves the speed of learning grammar and vocabulary as well. Also, the undoubted technical advantages of this method include the ability to use interactive video and audio clips in teaching oral speech. Demonstrating diagrams, photos, and drawings on the subject of language communication, the principle of clarity is realized. The introduction of multimedia technologies creates conditions for interactive communication, which today is the most important component of the educational process. Using multimedia technologies, the teacher can present information in a completely new and effective form, make it more complete, interesting, and close to the subject of communication being studied. Multimedia tools allow learners to utilize almost all the senses of learners, combining printed text, graphics, moving video, still photos, and audio, creating a real communication in English. It is proved that the use of multimedia materials and computer networks reduces learning time by almost three times, and the level of memorization through the simultaneous use of images, sound, text increases by 30-40 percent in fact.

Knowledge transfer to stimulate innovative thinking

To develop and cultivate pupils' creativity is an important subject which is highly valued and widely studied by educators all over the world. In the process of teaching, we should use all available teaching means to stimulate pupils' innovative spirit and cultivate their innovative thinking and ability so as to cultivate more versatile and creative talents. In the classroom teaching, we use

multimedia with a wide range, large capacity, more information, illustrated features, to attract pupils' attention, shorten the feedback time and organize pupils to extend and transfer the knowledge learned, stimulate their innovative thinking ability. For example, after teaching the dialogue of the text, multimedia display can be used to present the situation similar to the content of the text, encourage pupils to play their imagination in the simulated situation, use what they have learned to

compile the dialogue and act out the dialogue, which not only consolidates the learned knowledge, but also expands and extends the knowledge.

Although multimedia assisted teaching has many advantages. However, it is obviously unpractical to think that multimedia technology can completely replace traditional teaching means and one-sided pursuit of sensory effect, so that some problems that could be clearly expressed in a few words should be expressed in a large number of complex multimedia forms. And a good courseware should be through the careful design, artistic works, should fully embody the teachers' teaching structure, teaching thought, rather than the simple words and pictures, all the training materials, questions and answers are input to the computer, is the multimedia teaching, in this way, not only don't work, but may also be gild the lily, to reinvent the wheel. Teachers should remember that teachers are the organizers of classroom teaching and multimedia technology can only be used as a means to serve classroom teaching. If the multimedia courseware is allowed to go its own way, and the teacher only concentrates on operating the computer, it is bound to attract the pupils' attention to the courseware form too much, reduce the communication between teachers and pupils, and thus ignore the teaching purpose. Therefore, teachers should properly use multimedia technology to assist English teaching, and should not misuse or misuse it. Otherwise, it will not play its due role.

As another resource of enhancing speaking skills in English as a EFL American educational reformer John Dewey at the turn of 19th and 20th century in the USA suggested Technology based teaching. . He is considered being an ideological father of TBL and the main figure of progressive education at that time. Dewey perceived a child as a complex human being and pursued students felt the inner urge for learning along with their realization of reasons for studying.

The main developed competencies are mainly personnel and social ones. It is quite likely that fast changing and less predictable working conditions these days will lead people to the necessity of changing employments repeatedly and thus

having the ability of learning something new is desired. Beyond any doubt it is TBL that makes use of mutual cooperation and communication among students, in fact, it supports team cooperation and significant personnel characteristics like responsibility, autonomy or spirit of enterprise.

First of all, it is the student involvement into the choice of working that increases their inner motivation since all students bring into work their own ideas, view and individual approach. Herewith TBL serves for all abilities within a class and even relatively weak students may be able to use other talents valuable for collective success. Secondly, TBL provides contacts with reality and students may apply the knowledge they have theoretically learnt as well that students may try to solve practical problems. Next, it emerges that TBL enables to connect knowledge from other school subjects and students are to learn how to work with information from various sources, such as the Internet, books or information from friends, parents.

Next, one should also mention that TBL presumes realization of activities on programs mostly in teams which is another feature that students should be prepared to so that one day they can be prepared to work in successful teams. The issue of group work or group collaboration, which are specific teaching methods with their own rules, advantages and disadvantage, cannot be expanded on in this work, however, there will be written out main points and recommendations later on for their successful implementation into TBL. Origin, advantages and possible restrictions of TBL. Technology -Based Learning offers many advantages and challenges when implemented in the classroom. There are some strategies to successfully meet these challenges. But, as for the Boss, Krajcik, and Patrick (1995), some of the advantages of the PBL technique in learning are:

1. Increase in motivation: learners can choose their own topics, the extent of content, and the presentation mode. Learners build their projects to suit their own interests and abilities. These kinds of activities are highly motivating for learners.

2. Increase in problem-solving abilities: Project-Based Learning encourages learners to engage in complex and ill-defined contexts. From the beginning, learners identify their topics and their problems, and then seek possible solutions. By participating in both independent work and collaboration, learners improve their problem solving skills thereby developing their critical thinking skills.

3. Improves media research skills: Project-Based Learning provides a real world connection to context. Learners conduct research using multiple information resources. By locating the resources themselves, their research skills develop and improve. Increases in collaboration: in the processing stages, learners create and organize their own groups. They share knowledge and collaboratively construct artifacts. Through collaboration, they develop social communication skills and obtain multiple perspectives.

4. Increases in resource-management skills: successful Project-Based Learning provides learners with experience in project organization and time management with necessary scheduling of resources.

The Project-Based Learning technique offers many advantages when it is implemented in the classroom. Some of the advantages are increased motivation and

improved problem-solving abilities, collaboration and communication skills, creative and critical thinking skills, media research skills, and resource management skills.

To sum up, Technology-based teaching method suitable for the psychological characteristics of pupils, and the application of Technology-based can achieve good results in the innovation of college English translation education. Pupils have very flexible thinking. Only by activating pupils' interest in appropriate and reasonable ways can pupils learn more actively, and the efficiency of classroom teaching can be improved. Innovation in education encourages teachers and pupils to explore, research and use all the tools to uncover something

new. It involves a different way of looking at problems and solving them. The thinking process that goes into it will help pupils develop their creativity and their problem solving skills. The students made good improvement in some aspects of speaking skills such as pronunciation, vocabulary, accuracy and fluency. Moreover, it also changed the students' behavior. They were more confident to speak English and got more actively involved in the teaching-learning process. In addition, they had many more opportunities to speak. Furthermore, they were motivated to bring dictionaries to help themselves in the learning of the speaking skills. Also, the activities of the Project-Based Learning Technique made the class atmosphere more enjoyable.

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